

Maximizing the Volume of a Cylinder Inscribed in a Cone: Algebraic Approaches

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1 Introduction

Given a cone with a fixed base radius r and height h , we want to determine the dimensions (radius and height) of a right circular cylinder that can be inscribed within the cone such that the volume of the cylinder is maximized. This problem is a classic application of calculus and optimization, where the geometric constraints are used to express the volume as a function of one variable, and differentiation is used to find the optimal solution. In this paper, I present two distinct algebraic approaches to solving the problem, entirely avoiding the use of calculus.

Problem Statement

Given a cone with a fixed base radius r and height h , determine the values of x (the radius of the cylinder) and y (the height of the cylinder) that maximize the volume of a right circular cylinder inscribed within the cone.

2 Proof 1

From triangle congruency we get

$$\frac{\text{Height of the triangle above the cylinder}}{\text{Base of the triangle above the cylinder}} = \frac{\text{Height of the large triangle}}{\text{Base of the large triangle}}$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{h-y}{2x} = \frac{h}{2r} \implies (h-y)2r = 2xh \implies h-y = \frac{2xh}{2r} \implies y = h - \frac{2xh}{2r} = h\left(1 - \frac{x}{r}\right)$$

And, also

$$V = \pi x^2 y$$

Figure 1: Side View

Thus, we get :

$$V_k = \pi x^2 h \left(1 - \frac{x}{r}\right) = \pi h \left(x^2 - \frac{x^3}{r}\right) = \frac{\pi h}{r} (x^2 r - x^3)$$

Here , $\frac{\pi h}{r}$ is a positive constant, so V_k is maximized when $x^2 r - x^3$ is maximized.

$$x^2 r - x^3 = 4 \left(\frac{x}{2}\right)^2 (r - x)$$

By the AM-GM inequality we know ,

$$\frac{\frac{x}{2} + \frac{x}{2} + (r - x)}{3} \geq \sqrt[3]{\frac{x}{2} \cdot \frac{x}{2} (x - r)} \iff$$

$$\left(\frac{r}{3}\right)^3 \geq \left(\frac{x}{2}\right)^2 (x - r) \iff 4 \left(\frac{r}{3}\right)^3 \geq 4 \left(\frac{x}{2}\right)^2 (x - r)$$

And , the equality holds only when $\frac{x}{2} = r - x$. Substituting that into our formula for V_k :

$$\begin{aligned} \max V_k = \frac{\pi h}{r} (x^2 r - x^3) &\xrightarrow{x=\frac{2r}{3}} \max V_k = \frac{\pi h}{r} \left(\left(\frac{2r}{3}\right)^2 r - \left(\frac{2r}{3}\right)^3 \right) = \frac{\pi h}{r} \left(\frac{4r^2}{9} r - \frac{8r^3}{27} \right) = \\ &= \frac{\pi h}{r} \left(\frac{12r^3 - 8r^3}{27} \right) \implies \end{aligned}$$

$$\max V_k = \pi h r^2 \frac{4}{27}$$

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3 Proof 2

We have:

$$V = \pi h x^2 \left(1 - \frac{x}{r}\right)$$

$$V = -\frac{\pi h}{r} x^2 (x - r)$$

This is a cubic function with leading coefficient $-\frac{\pi h}{r}$, a double root at $x = 0$, and a single root at $x = r$. Here is the graph:

We want to find the coordinates of the local maximum point, without calculus, as requested.

Translate the curve down so that the local maximum point becomes a tangent point with the x -axis.

The new curve's equation can be expressed as $V = -\frac{\pi h}{r} x^2 (x - r) - k$ for some k , and it can also be expressed as $V = -\frac{\pi h}{r} (x - a)(x - b)^2$ for some a and b , where b is the x -coordinate of the local maximum point.

Set these two expressions equal:

$$-\frac{\pi h}{r} x^2 (x - r) - k = -\frac{\pi h}{r} (x - a)(x - b)^2$$

Divide both sides by $-\frac{\pi h}{r}$ and expand:

$$x^3 - rx^2 + \frac{kr}{\pi h} = x^3 - (a + 2b)x^2 + (2ab + b^2)x - ab^2$$

Equate coefficients on the left and right:

$$x^2 : r = a + 2b$$

$$x^1 : 0 = 2ab + b^2$$

Solving these two equations together (keeping in mind that $a < 0$ and $0 < b < r$), we get $a = -\frac{1}{3}r$ and $b = \frac{2}{3}r$.

So the volume of the cylinder is maximized when $x = \frac{2}{3}r$ and $y = \frac{1}{3}h$.

The maximum volume of the cylinder is $k = -ab^2 \left(\frac{\pi h}{r} \right) = \frac{4\pi}{27}hr^2$.

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